
Research Article

Assessing Fish Production in Four Local Government Areas of Kwara State

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Abstract

This study assessed fish production in four (4) Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Thirty (30) fish farmers based on availability were surveyed in this study. The stratified sampling technique was used to carry out the survey. Youths within the age bracket of 31 – 40 years of age dominated the fish farmers in the surveyed area. Findings revealed that majority of them were married and learned. Quite a number of them were discovered to be government workers who use their personal savings to run fish farming business. About 90% were into catfish production. Earthen pond rearing structure and stream/river water source were mostly used by the fish farmers. This study was purposely carried out to ascertain the level of fish farming operation in the state by assessing their performance and see possible areas to address by providing way forward in enhancing fish production in Kwara State.

Key words: fish, farmers, assessing, survey, state, production.

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Introduction

Aquaculture has primarily been a developing world activity, especially in Asian countries. Asia alone accounts for 87% of global aquaculture production, while China is responsible for about 68% of the global production. In 1997, India and Southeast Asia accounted for about 15% of production (Delgado *et al.*, 2003). Worldwide, fish production has grown dramatically in the last 50 years with fish food supply outgrowing world population growth (FAO, 2014). The livelihoods of millions are

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dependent on fish farming and the fishery industry is crucial to the world economy (Nwachukwu and Onuegbu, 2007).

In Africa, the fish sector provides income for over 10 million people engaged in fish production, processing and trade (NEPAD, 2005). It is estimated that Africa produced 7.3 million tonnes in 2003, and about 80% of this is produced by just two countries which are Nigeria and Egypt (FAO, 2011). Nigerians are high fish consumers and offer the largest market for fish and fishery products in Africa (Olaoye and Oloruntoba, 2011).

Fishing like other hunting activities has been a major source of food for the human race and has put an end to the unsavory outbreak of anemia, kwashiorkor, etc. It accounts for about one-fifth of the world total supply of animal protein and this has risen five folds over the last forty years from 20 million metric tonnes to 98 million metric tons in 1993 and projected to exceed 150 million metric tons by the year 2010 (FAO, 1991). Fishery is an important food production subsector, providing almost 20% of the world's protein supply. However, trends have shown that fish production from capture fisheries has reached its limit, which calls for an increase in fish supply from aquaculture (FAO, 2012). It is hoped that aquaculture production will increase fish supply and bridge the ever increasing gap between fish supply and demand.

The fisheries subsector occupies a unique position in the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy as it contributes about one-tenth of the GDP to the sector (FDF, 2008). Its prospect continues to increase due to the huge gap between fish demand and supply which leaves a shortfall of about 680,000 metric tons of fish annually necessitating government importation of fish worth ₦97 billion annually (Adekunle, 2013). Fish farming generates employment directly and indirectly in terms of people employed in the production of fishing output and other allied business. It also generates income for all categories of people involved in fish farming and thus contributes to the national income.

The composition of overall fisheries production has steadily shifted away from developed countries towards developing countries. Delgado *et al.* (2003) stated that even though developing countries have doubled the size of fish production since 1973, the production from developed countries has remained virtually unchanged. Therefore, there is need to research on the level of fish production in Kwara State as to provide information on fish farming in order to aid its policy formulation and development. In view of this, the study which focused on four Local Government Areas of Kwara State sought to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the fish farmers, identify major

activities carried out in the various fish farms, know the type of feed they feed their fish with and also know the means by which they have access to information on modern technology related to fish production.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Kwara State. The State shares boundaries with Oyo, Osun and Ekiti to the South, Kogi and Niger to the North, Kogi to the East and Republic of Benin on the West side. Kwara State has sixteen Local Government Areas. It has an estimated population of about 2.3 million people (NPC 2006), a figure which is assumed to have substantially increased. Kwara State is located in the North-Central geopolitical zone (middle-belt) of Nigeria in the areas that extend roughly from latitude (60301 to 110051) north of the equator and longitude (2051 to 70451) east of the prime meridian. This area is largely located in the savannah region of Nigeria. It is an ecological transition zone between the arid north and the moist south with temperature fluctuating between 30°C and 37°C in the year and rainfall of 1000 to 1500 mm annually. The study area has two distinct climatic seasons, the wet (Rainy) and dry (Harmattan) seasons. The rainfall across the two seasons extends between November and February. This climatic condition as well as fertile soil makes the State favorable for arable crop production such as rice, millet, yam, cowpea etc. (KWARA MANR, 2012).

Data collection

Collection of data was carried out using a well-structured questionnaire. These questionnaires were administered to respondents between October 2018 and March 2019. The stratified sampling technique was adopted for the survey exercise which was based on the number of available farmers into fish production in the selected LGAs. Fish farmers were randomly selected from four different Local Government Areas of the State namely Asa, Ilorin South, Ilorin East and Ifelodun.

In this study, the data collected include socio-economic characteristics of the fish farmers, major activities carried out by the fish farmers in their farms and means of accessing information on modern technology related to fish farming.

Statistical tool

Data obtained from the respondents into fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics

Age

Thirty fish farmers were sourced based on availability within the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Out of these 30 fish farmers, four of them representing 13.33% were in the age bracket of 21 - 30 years, 12 of them representing 40% fell within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years, nine of them representing 30% fell within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years and five of them representing 16.67% fell within the age bracket of 50 years and above. This signifies that youths within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years of age dominated the fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas surveyed in Kwara State.

Sex

Out of the 30 fish farmers who responded to the questionnaires, 25 of them representing 83.33% were males while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% were females. This signifies that there are more male fish farmers than female fish farmers in the fish farming business in the surveyed area.

Marital status

Among the 30 fish farmers surveyed, twenty-four of them representing 80% were found to be married, five of them representing 16.67% were single and one of them representing 3.33% was found to be a widow. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers in the area surveyed were married.

Household size

Out of the 30 fish farmers, fifteen of them representing 50% have a household size of 0 - 5 people, nine of them representing 30% have a household size of 6 - 10 people, one of them representing 3.33% have a household size of 11 - 15 people while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% of the fish farmers failed to declare their household size. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers involved in the study had a household size of 0 - 5 people.

Educational level

Out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the survey, twenty-two of them representing 73.33% had tertiary education, four of them representing 13.33% had high school education, while one respondent each representing 3.33% had primary education, adult education and no formal education, respectively. Also, one of the respondents

representing 3.33% declined to give information related to his educational status. Almost all the fish farmers in the study area had tertiary education.

Years of experience in fish farming

Twenty-seven (27) out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed representing 90% had between one - 10 years of fish farming experience while the remaining three fish farmers representing 10% had between 11 - 20 years of fish farming experience. This simply shows that almost all the farmers involved in the study area had between 1 - 10 years of fish farming experience.

Religion

Among the 30 fish farmers, sixteen of them representing 53.33% were Christians while the remaining fourteen representing 46.67% practiced Islam. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers involved in the surveyed area were Christians.

Supplementary job with fish farming business

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed, 7 representing 23.33% were involved in crop farming to augment fish farming business, two of them representing 6.67% were involved in trading business as well, eleven of them representing 36.67% were government workers who were using fish farming to supplement their earnings, four of them representing 13.33% were involved in other vocational jobs, two of them representing 6.67% were commercial drivers who are using fish farming to supplement their incomes and one of them representing 3.33% was involved in both crop farming and trading business with the fish farming business he is into. In addition to this, one of them representing 3.33% was involved in both vocation job and trading business to supplement his fish farming business. However, two of the fish farmers representing 6.67% were fully into fish farming business as they have no other business to engage in. This is to say that most of these fish farmers were government workers who needed to supplement the little they are earning from fish farming business to support their financial obligations.

Mode of land acquisition

Nineteen (19) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 63.33% acquired their land through purchase, five of them representing 16.67% acquired their land through lease/rent, four of them representing 13.33% acquired their land through inheritance while the remaining two representing 6.67% obtained their land through gift. Most of the fish farmers involved in the study area obtained their lands through purchase.

Purpose of involvement in fish farming

Thirteen (13) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 43.33% became involved in fish farming business purposely to make profit, seven of them representing 23.33% got involved in fish farming business purposely to augment their income, three of them representing 10% got involved in fish farming business as a means of survival, six of them representing 20% became involved in fish farming business due to show of interest. However, one of them representing 3.33% failed to choose the reason for his involvement in fish farming business. Interestingly among those that picked their reasons, it was discovered that none of them chose the business for the purpose of home consumption which really indicates that home consumption was not by any means a reason for venturing into the business. The outcome of the respondents showed that the main reason for venturing into fish farming business was to make profit.

Membership of cooperative society

Among the 30 fish farmers, ten of them representing 33.33% belong to a cooperative society, nineteen of them representing 63.33% did not belong to any cooperative society while one of them representing 3.33% failed to respond. This is to say that few of the fish farmers were in one cooperative society or the other as many were not involved.

Source of finance

Out of the 30 fish farmers in the surveyed area, twenty-four of them representing 80% sourced their fund from personal savings, four of them representing 13.33% sourced their fund from cooperative society, one of them representing 3.33% sourced his fund from bank loan while one of them representing 3.33% failed to respond. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers used their personal savings to run their fish farming business.

Fish species reared

Out of the 30 respondents, twenty-seven of them representing 90% are into catfish production, one of them representing 3.33% was into heterobranchus production, one of them representing 3.33% was into tilapia production while the remaining one respondent representing 3.33% was into production of both catfish and heterobranchus.

Fish Species in demand

All the 30 fish farmers in the surveyed area reported that catfish was more demanding among the people patronizing them.

Major activities carried out in the various fish farms

Source of water

Out of the four sources of water available in the study area, fourteen out of the 30 fish farmers representing 46.67% reported using stream or river water for their fish pond, eight out of them representing 26.67% reported using deep well water for their fish pond, seven out of them representing 23.33% reported using borehole water for their fish pond while the remaining one representing 3.33% reported using pipe-borne water for his fish pond. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers in the surveyed area used stream or river water for their fish pond.

Water analysis

Eleven (11) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 36.67% reported carrying out water analysis before stocking their fish while the remaining nineteen representing 63.33% reported not carrying out water analysis before stocking their fish.

Rearing structure

Out of the seven rearing structures available in the study area, twelve out of the 30 fish farmers representing 40% reported using only earthen pond, ten out of them representing 33.33% reported using only plastic basins, three out of them representing 10% reported using the combination of earthen pond and concrete pond, two out of them representing 6.67% reported using only trampoline, one out of them each representing 3.33% reported using concrete pond, fish trough and combination of plastic basin and trampoline, respectively. This signifies that many of the fish farmers involved in the study area use earthen pond only.

Source of fingerlings

Nineteen (19) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 63.33% reported sourcing their fingerlings through private fish hatchery, while five of them each representing 16.67% reported sourcing their fingerlings through personal fish hatchery and government fish hatchery, respectively. Only one of them representing 3.33% failed to provide information on the source of his fingerlings. This signifies that many of the fish farmers involved in the study area sourced their fingerlings through private fish hatchery.

Cultural fish farming practice

Out of the two cultural fish farming practice adopted in the study area, twenty-eight out of the 30 fish farmers representing 93.33% adopted monoculture fish farming practice while the remaining two representing 6.67% adopted polyculture fish farming practice.

This signifies that almost all the fish farmers in the study area practiced monoculture system of rearing fish. This is a situation whereby only a fish species is being reared.

Materials used for fingerlings transportation

Out of the five transport materials available in the study area, twenty-eight out of the 30 fish farmers representing 93.33% reported the use of kegs in transporting their fingerlings, one of them representing 3.33% reported the use of plastic bags in transporting his fingerlings while the remaining one representing 3.33% failed to respond. This implies that most of the fish farmers in the study area use kegs as a medium for transporting their fingerlings from the hatchery after purchase. This study also tells us that none of the fish farmers in the surveyed area made use of buckets, drums and oxygen bags as other mediums used for transporting fingerlings.

Duration of fish culture

Fourteen (14) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 46.67% reared their fish for 6 months, ten of them representing 33.33% reared their fish for 5 months, three of them representing 10% reared their fish for 4 months, while same three representing 10% reared their fish for 6 months and above. This signifies that most fish farmers in the study area reared their fish for 6 months.

Harvesting time per year

Twenty-three (23) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 76.67% harvested their fish two times in a year, five of them representing 16.67% reported harvesting their fish three times in a year while one of them each representing 3.33% reported harvesting their fish once and four times in a year, respectively. This signifies that most fish farmers in the study area harvested their fish two times in a year.

Pond protection from predators

Out of the 30 fish farmers, seventeen of them representing 56.67% used the netting system to protect their fish ponds, seven of them representing 23.33% used fencing system to protect their fish ponds, three of them representing 10% used the combination of netting and fencing systems to protect their fish ponds, one of them representing 3.33% used the combination of roofing and netting systems to protect his fish pond while one of them representing 3.33% failed to respond. This implies that most of the fish farmers used netting system to protect their fish ponds.

Mode of feeding fish

Nineteen (19) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 63.33% used primitive method to feed their fish, nine of them representing 30% applied body weight requirements to feed their fish while two of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers used the primitive method to feed their fish.

Source of fish feed raw materials

Out of the 30 fish farmers, fourteen of them representing 46.67% used the combination of foreign and local feed materials in producing their fish feed, eleven of them representing 36.67% used foreign feed materials to produce their fish feed while five of them representing 16.67% used local feed materials to produce their fish feed. This signifies that larger percentage of fish farmers prefer the combination of foreign and local feed materials when formulating their fish feed.

Nature of feed type

There are three types of feeds namely pelleted, granulated and powdered in which each feed type has three different submersion capacity feeds, namely, floating, semi floating and non-floating. Among the 30 fish farmers that picked pelleted feed type, seventeen of them representing 56.67% reported using floating capacity feed, three of them representing 10% reported using semi-floating capacity feed, six of them representing 20% reported using non-floating capacity feed, one of them representing 3.33% reported using the combination of floating and non-floating capacity feed while the remaining three representing 10% said they were not familiar with pelleted feed.

In the case of the 30 fish farmers that picked granulated feed type, it was observed that one of them each representing 3.33% reported using floating and semi-floating capacity feed, respectively. Nine (9) of them representing 30% reported using non floating capacity feed while the remaining nineteen representing 63.33% said they were not familiar with granulated feed.

Considering those that picked powdered feed type among the 30 fish farmers, it was observed that one representing 3.33% in each case used floating, semi floating and non-floating capacity feed, respectively. The remaining twenty-seven representing 90% were not familiar with powdered feed. It can be deduced from this study that pelleted feed type is the most commonly known feed to fish farmers in the surveyed area.

Sourcing for information on modern technology

The questionnaire administered provided eight means for sourcing of information in respect to modern technology in assisting fish farmers to increase their production. The eight means include symposium, internet, journals, text books, seminar, training, television and radio programme. Each means was provided with four options namely very often, often, rarely and never.

Symposium

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, one of them representing 3.33% indicated that he attends symposium on fish farming very often, four of them representing 13.33% indicated that they attend symposium on fish farming often, twenty of them representing 66.67% indicated that they rarely attend symposium on fish farming while the remaining five representing 16.67% never attended symposium on fish farming. This means that hardly do the majority of these farmers attend symposium that can improve their fish farming business.

Internet

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, ten of them representing 33.33% indicated using internet very often, eight of them representing 26.67% indicated using internet often, ten of them representing 33.33% indicated that they rarely use internet while the remaining two representing 6.67% never used internet. This implies that equal number of fish farmers use the internet facility very often as likewise those that rarely use it.

Journal information

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, three of them representing 10% indicated using journal information on fish farming very often, five of them representing 16.67% indicated using journal information on fish farming often, nineteen of them representing 63.33% indicated that they rarely use journal information on fish farming while the remaining three representing 10% never used journal information on fish farming. Most of the fish farmers rarely use journal information on fish farming.

Textbooks

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, three of them representing 10% indicated using textbooks on fish farming very often, six of them representing 20% indicated using textbooks on fish farming often, eighteen of them representing 60% indicated that they rarely use textbooks on fish farming while the

remaining 3 representing 10% never used textbooks on fish farming. Most of the fish farmers rarely use textbooks related to fish farming to improve their fish farming business.

Seminar

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, three of them representing 10% indicated that they attend seminar on fish farming very often, eleven of them representing 36.67% indicated that they attend seminar on fish farming often, twelve of them representing 40% indicated that they rarely attend seminar on fish farming while the remaining four representing 13.33% never attended seminar on fish farming. Quite a number of fish farmers involved in the survey area sincerely appreciate the new information they receive on fish farming through attending seminars compared to the number of those that falls under rarely and never group.

Training

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, six of them representing 20% indicated that they go for training programme on fish farming very often, nine of them representing 30% indicated that they go for training programme on fish farming often, ten of them representing 33.33% indicated that they rarely go for training programme on fish farming while the remaining five representing 16.67% never went for training programme on fish farming. Equal number of fish farmers goes for training program on fish farming when compared to those that never or rarely go for training on fish farming.

Television

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, four of them representing 13.33% indicated that they watch television programme on fish farming very often, ten of them representing 33.33% indicated that they watch television programme on fish farming often, eleven of them representing 36.67% indicated that they rarely watch television programme on fish farming while the remaining five representing 16.67% never watched television programme on fish farming. We can deduce that we have a fewer number of fish farmers that watch television programme on fish farming than those that never or rarely watch television programme on fish farming.

Radio

Out of the 30 fish farmers that were administered the questionnaire, five of them representing 16.67% indicated listening to radio programme on fish farming very often,

nine of them representing 30% indicated listening to radio programme on fish farming often, twelve of them representing 40% indicated that they rarely listen to radio programme on fish farming while the remaining four representing 13.33% never listened to any radio programme on fish farming. We noticed more of the fish farmers fall in the group of those that listens to radio programme on fish farming than those in the rarely group.

Conclusion and Way Forward

A survey was carried out to access fish production in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. The fish farmers who were 30 in number comprises of youths within the age bracket of 31 – 40 years of age who were mainly males. Eighty percent were married and found to study up to tertiary education level. About 90% were found to have up to 1 – 10 years of experience in fish farming. Government workers dominated the highest percentage of those who were fish farmers in the surveyed area. Eighty percent of these fish farmers claimed to use their personal savings to run their fish farming business. About 90% of these fish farmers were into catfish production.

The study also showed that majority of the fish farmers used stream/ river water source for their fish pond which comprises mainly of earthen pond. Majority of these fish farmers sourced their fingerlings from private fish hatchery. Most of the fish farmers in the surveyed area reared their fish for 6 months by feeding them with both local and foreign pelleted feed by utilizing the primitive method of feeding.

As regards sourcing for information to enhance fish production, most of the fish farmers get their information through the use of internet, this was followed by attending training programmes on fish farming. Furthermore, attending seminars, watching television programmes and listening to radio programmes on fish farming also helped the fish farmers in sourcing for information.

From this study we would like to provide the following way forward for fish farmers in the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State: -

1. The primitive way of feeding as discovered to be commonly used in this study is a setback to fish production. Therefore, fish farmers are encouraged to feed according to the body weight of the fish in order to make profit at the end of the production cycle. This body weight feeding pattern will also help to avoid polluting the pond water with unconsumed feed.

2. Earthen pond as commonly used in the study area is meant to reduce the cost of feeding by enabling the fish utilize the micro flora and fauna in the earthen pond water as supplementary feed source for the fish. Therefore, fish farmers are to reduce the fish feed input by 25% as they consider these microorganisms (micro flora and fauna) in the earthen pond as supplementary feed for the fish.
3. Fish farmers are advised to improve on their means of sourcing for information as it was discovered that majority of the respondents fell under rarely and never options of sourcing for information. The importance of sourcing for information is to be abreast with new techniques and advancement in fish production.
4. Fish farmers are expected to carry out proper water analysis before stocking their fish pond. This will help to reduce undue mortality and outbreak of infections in the pond as a result of water pH variations. In this study, it was discovered that most of the fish farmers did not carry out water analysis before stocking their fish ponds which amounts to high risk of mortality and outbreak of infections in the pond.
5. We encourage the participation of those within the age bracket of 21 - 30 years of age in fish farming production in Kwara State as this will help reduce the rate of unemployment in the State. This was found to be the lowest among the age groups in the surveyed area.
6. Commercial banks are encouraged to make loan available to fish farmers to enable them boost their production. A situation whereby just one fish farmer had access to bank loan among the thirty fish farmers involved in the study portrays the negative impression that banks have towards fish farming business in the State.
7. In order to maximize profit in fish production, fish farmers are expected to have full concentration on the business by not trying to join it with any other full time job. The case of having the majority as government workers as shown in this study would not give room for full concentration on the business thereby making the business not as lucrative as expected.

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